

Solar-Blind Free-Space QKD Using Large-Core Fibers for Alignment-Tolerant Link Operation

Florian Honz⁽¹⁾, Winfried Boxleitner⁽¹⁾, Michael Hentschel⁽¹⁾, Philip Walther⁽²⁾, Hannes Hübel⁽¹⁾, and Bernhard Schrenk⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Center for Digital Safety & Security, Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria

⁽²⁾University of Vienna, Faculty of Physics, Vienna Center for Quantum Science and Technology (VCQ), Boltzmannngasse 5, 1090 Vienna, Austria

Author e-mail address: florian.honz@ait.ac.at

ABSTRACT

While fiber-optic quantum key distribution (QKD) systems have reached a technological maturity that permits field deployments, the complexity of free-space optical (FSO) QKD systems introduced to ensure minimal coupling loss over air hinders the use of QKD in fiber-scarce environments. As a response to this challenge, we present a simplified approach that leverages large-core fibers at the receiving air interface of short-range terrestrial FSO links. We show that the increased sensitivity to solar irradiance, as it arises from the adoption of alignment-tolerant multi-mode fibers, can be effectively mitigated through a spectral E-band allocation of the QKD channel. We accomplish a secure-key rate of 869 b/s/detector for a 63-m long outdoor free-space link during day-light operation at 42.9 klux, despite employing a 25- μm core fiber at Bob's QKD receiver. We further demonstrate the co-existence of a classical data stream over the solar-blind FSO QKD link.

INTRODUCTION

The security of the currently employed asymmetric security protocols is threatened by the rapid development of quantum computers. Their computational power has reached more than 1000 physical qubits [1] while a steady increase can be observed for the efficiency of error-correcting codecs [2]. The potential of an eavesdropper who harvests data for later decryption with a powerful-enough quantum computer clearly highlights the urgency to secure today's communications through an information-theoretic secure approach. Such is offered by quantum key distribution (QKD), which guarantees data security by the laws of nature. While first commercial QKD systems have already been deployed in fiber networks, this is not yet the case for free-space optical (FSO) QKD systems. However, there is a need to provide a lightpath continuum to support QKD also in fiber-scarce environments. The lack of maturity of FSO QKD solutions results from the need for active alignment of the transmitter and receiver terminals [3-9], as well as the size of the usually employed telescopes to ensure a good coupling efficiency [3-6]. In addition, FSO systems are inevitably exposed to sunlight. The probability of direct exposure has been estimated to reach up to 1% [10]. Yet, the impact of solar irradiance is detrimental since photodetection needs to be carried out at the single-photon level [6-9]. While current results on terrestrial FSO QKD systems have achieved key-rates in the kb/s range for a QBER as low as 0.5% under full daylight [3] and accomplished distances up to 20 km compatible for operation independent of the daytime [6], these systems necessitate excessive spatial and spectral filtering together with fast beam steering mirrors [3, 4, 6, 7, 9]. This system complexity calls for a simplified approach that enables the widespread deployment of free-space terrestrial QKD solutions. Moreover, miniaturization through photonic integration is paramount to further reduce size and cost, as already demonstrated in [3].

This work extends our initial investigation [11] of an outdoor free-space QKD setup based on large-core fiber optics. We rely on the atmospheric absorption of solar photons traversing the atmosphere in the E-band to enable solar-blind operation for our short reach terrestrial QKD link (Fig. 1). Furthermore, a reduction of the detrimental effect of depolarization on the QKD signal during large-core fiber transmission at the receiver side is paramount. To this end, we investigate the influence of mode-filtering on the polarization extinction ratio and QKD performance for a 25- μm core multi-mode fiber (MMF) at the receiver terminal. In addition, we evaluate the benefits of photonic integration at the transmitter side. However, since the current photonic integration platforms are optimized for C-band operation [12] and do not natively support the E-band, we compare the performance of our LiNbO₃-based state encoder at 1410 nm and 1550.5 nm with a silicon photonic integrated circuit (PIC) operated at 1550.5 nm.

This manuscript is organized as follows. Section II introduces the concept of large core-optics and solar-blind operation,

Fig. 1. The asymmetry in lightpath length between the sunlight traversing the atmosphere (L_S) and the terrestrial FSO link (L_T) can be harnessed to achieve solar-blind QKD, benefitting from the E-band absorption window in the atmosphere.

TABLE I
CONFIGURATION OF FSO QKD IMPLEMENTATIONS AND FSO CHANNELS CHARACTERISTICS.

Spectral allocation	Alice		Transmission channel		Bob	Co-existing classical data channel
	QKD Transmitter	λ_Q [nm]	FSO link	Receiving fiber	QKD Receiver	
E-Band	DFB + PolMux-I/Q	1390	outdoor (63 m) indoor (6 m)	SMF 25- μ m MMF 50- μ m OM4 MMF	InGaAs SPAD: ~10% efficiency 25 μ s dead time 300 cts/s	1 Gb/s 1547.72 nm
		1410				
		1433				
C-band	DFB + PolMux-I/Q	1550.5	indoor (6 m)	25- μ m MMF (6 m)	InGaAs SPADs: ~10% efficiency 25 μ s dead time 427 & 400 cts/s	-
	DFB + Silicon PIC	1550.5				

while Section III introduces the experimental framework that has been used to evaluate the QKD implementations. Section IV discusses the performance of the indoor FSO QKD link and the impact on the signal integrity when a MMF is adopted within the lightpath. Section V then reports the performance for an outdoor FSO QKD link. Finally, Section VI concludes the work.

SOLAR-BLIND QKD WITH LARGE-CORE OPTICS

Coupling from an ITU-T G.652 compatible single-mode fiber (SMF) with a core diameter of 8.2 μ m to a second SMF core over a free-space link represents an enormous challenge for FSO deployments. In order to relax the requirements on the receiver side and enhance the alignment tolerance at the same time, we therefore propose the use of large-core fibers at the receiving terminal. As we have recently demonstrated [13], the use of large-core fibers enables a fully-passive FSO deployment by enhancing the alignment tolerance and reducing the impact of atmospheric turbulence [14]. Here, we evaluate three different receiving fibers in view of different FSO links: First, a standard telecom SMF is employed to obtain a reference scenario. Second, we will employ a step-index MMF with a core diameter of 25 μ m, which is compared to a graded-index OM4 MMF with 50 μ m core diameter as the third option.

We evaluated these fibers over a 6-m long indoor FSO bridge as well as over a 63-m long outdoor FSO link, employing commercially available fiber collimators. These collimators widen the FSO beams to a diameter of \sim 8 mm at the transmitter and receiver terminals, and are tailored with respect to their numerical aperture for use with either the SMF or the MMFs. The deployment of both FSO links was followed by an initial manual alignment. The alignment was then frozen for the entire duration of the experiment. All tested configurations are summarized in Table I.

While SMFs inherently filter sunlight relatively well due to their small core diameter and reduced acceptance angle, the expanded diameter and increased numerical aperture of large-core fibers reduces these spatial filtering capabilities, which

Fig. 2. (a) Single-photon spectrum of the solar background acquired over several days. (b) Optical spectra for classical channel, filter transmission T and solar background S . (c) Solar irradiance during QKD evaluation on a single day in autumn.

renders the QKD link vulnerable to solar irradiance. However, due to the water vapor present in the atmosphere there exists a region in the E-band between 1350 and 1450 nm, where the solar irradiance is reduced due to absorption [15]. By allocating the quantum channel to this spectral region, we can reduce the detrimental impact of solar irradiance. In this way, we can build on the asymmetry between the short distance of our terrestrial FSO link compared to the thickness of the atmosphere (Fig. 1), to eventually enable QKD despite the use of large-core optics.

To prove this point of sunlight-agnostic operation, we first conducted a long-term characterization concerning the coupling of solar background photons into a 50- μm OM4 fiber. We used a single-photon spectrometer with 10% detection efficiency and 12 dB of coupling loss due to the roof-top feeder fiber and the insertion loss of its grating before the single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD, Fig. 2(a)). As can be seen, there is a wide spectral notch that covers more than four coarse wavelength division multiplexing (CWDM) channels at ~ 1400 nm. In this window that is attributed to the absorption of light in the atmosphere, we primarily measure dark counts at <26 dBHz/nm. Apart from the periodic day- and night-time cycles, Fig. 2 also shows the passing of clouds, as they are exemplarily annotated during the first day of the measurement (α).

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP OF THE FSO QKD LINKS

Figure 3 presents the experimental setup used to evaluate the performance of the in- and outdoor QKD links.

A. Polarization-multiplexed I/Q Modulator Transmitter

For the quantum transmitter, distributed feedback (DFB) lasers at $\lambda_{Qi} = \{1390, 1410, 1433, 1550.5 \text{ nm}\}$ and thus within the spectral region of interest were used as photon sources, together with the corresponding receiver-side CWDM filters, as highlighted in Fig. 2(b). The state-encoding in the right-/left-circular (R/L) and anti-/diagonal (A/D) bases for a polarization-based BB84 protocol was then performed via a polarization-multiplexed (PolMux) in-phase/quadrature (I/Q) modulator [16]. Since the states R, L, A and D only differ by the relative phase of the principal horizontal (H) and vertical (V) polarization states, the modulation of the I/Q modulator phase section via an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) is sufficient to generate these four polarization states. Due to the limited electro-optic bandwidth of 0.92 GHz for the I/Q phase electrode we resorted to operation at a symbol rate of $R_Q = 0.5$ Gbaud. To set the desired mean photon number to $\mu_Q = 0.1$ photons/symbol at the transmitter output, an additional variable optical attenuator (VOA) is employed. Any polarization drift along the feeder fibers at the transmitter- and receiver-side of the FSO link is compensated via a manual polarization controller (PC) following the transmitter.

B. PIC Transmitter

For the C-band wavelength (λ_{Q4}), we further replaced the LiNbO₃ based I/Q modulator with a more compact silicon PIC, dedicated for polarization modulation, for comparison. The PIC, which is shown in Fig. 3, is manufactured on a silicon-on-insulator platform and has a footprint of 2.5 mm². Light is coupled from a fiber to the PIC via a 1D grating coupler (GC) at an angle of 10°. The first phase modulation section PM1 is used in combination with a multi-mode interference (MMI) coupler that equally distributes the optical power between the two branches of the second phase modulation section PM2. Due to the 2D-GC used for coupling light out of the waveguide plane and back into the fiber, each branch of PM2 corresponds to one of the principal polarization states H and V. Depending on the induced phase shift between the branches the four desired polarization

Fig. 3. Experimental setup for the evaluation of large-core fibers as receiving air interface in FSO QKD links, employing either a polarization multiplexed I/Q-modulator or a silicon PIC-based polarization modulator at the transmitter.

Fig. 4. (a) Polarization extinction ratio and mode filter loss as a function of the number of fiber windings. (b) Polarization evolution over 1 minute for FSO coupling from SMF to SMF and SMF to MMF, the latter with and without mode filtering.

states **R**, **L**, **A** and **D** can therefore be generated via modulation of PM2 through the AWG. The total fiber-to-fiber loss including all PIC elements is 28 dB and primarily results from the long phase-shifter elements. Nonetheless, a VOA is required to set the desired mean photon number to $\mu_Q = 0.1$ photons/symbol at the transmitter output, similarly as for the I/Q modulator implementation. Any polarization drift along the feeder fibers is again compensated via a manual polarization controller (PC) at the transmitter side. While the PIC would in principle allow for modulation in the >10 GHz regime due to its fast electro-optic phase shifters, it was operated at an identical symbol rate of $R_Q = 0.5$ Gbaud for the sake of comparison.

C. Transmission Channel

The transmitted signal is then either fed to the roof-top installation through a 200-m SMF feeder fiber or directly connected to the indoor reference FSO link through a 10-m SMF patchcord. The optical end-to-end budget of the link between Alice and Bob was set via a VOA on Alice' side in order to investigate the QKD performance as a function of the channel loss.

D. Quantum Receiver and Background Photon Filtering

At Bob's side, the incoming quantum signal is coupled to a short piece of large-core fiber to relay the collected photons to a free-space polarization analyzer. This polarimeter-like sub-system is equipped with free-space polarizers and waveplates, which allows us to analyze the signal in the **H/V**, **R/L** and **A/D** bases. For the outdoor FSO QKD link measurements we then employed an InGaAs SPAD with a dead time of 25 μ s, a detection efficiency of 10% at 1550 nm and a dark count rate of 300 cts/s. For the indoor reference link, two InGaAs SPADs with identical dead time and detection efficiency but higher dark count rates of 427 cts/s and 400 cts/s, were employed. The detection events were recorded by a time-tagging module (TTM) with a resolution of 82.3 ps. After frame synchronization, temporal filtering was applied to 50% of the symbol width and a real-time raw-key rate and quantum bit error ratio (QBER) estimation was performed.

In order to remove any out-of-band background photons (S in Fig 2(b)) from the quantum signal at λ_{Qi} before the SPADs, a 50-nm wide free-space bandpass filter (BPF) is included in the polarization analyzer, together with a fiber-optic multi-mode CWDM A/D filter. This combination was chosen to leverage the high suppression of the free-space BPF over the entire SPAD responsivity window while at the same time benefiting from the low-insertion loss and narrower pass-window of the CWDM filter. For the wavelength channels λ_{Q1} and λ_{Q2} this filter cascade reduced the background noise below the dark-count level of the SPADs. It, therefore, compensates the poor spatial filtering of the FSO receiver due to the large-core fiber while the alignment of the FSO transmitter and receiver terminals is greatly simplified. For the channel at λ_{Q3} , which operates at the border of the water vapor absorption region, we measured an increased in-band noise floor of 590 cts/s. This is nearly twice the dark count rate.

E. Classical Data Co-Existence Setup

For the outdoor FSO link we additionally evaluated the robustness of the E-band quantum transmission to a classical C-band data channel operating at $\lambda_c = 1547.72$ (Fig. 2(b)). This channel was intensity modulated at a data rate of $R_c = 1$ Gb/s through on-off keying (OOK), using a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM). In order to clean the quantum channels from the typically far-reaching spontaneous emission tails of the classical channel, two 1550-nm CWDM add/drop (A/D) filters were employed at the classical data transmitter, followed by a VOA to calibrate the launch power of the data channel to 0 dBm. The classical and quantum signals were multiplexed via a red/blue (R/B) waveband filter (Fig. 2(b)).

The performance for classical data transmission was evaluated by means of real-time bit error ratio (BER) measurements after photodetection with a multi-mode avalanche photoreceiver (APD). Each measurement was performed over a period of several minutes for which the received optical power (ROP) was stable, as well as the BER.

BASELINE FSO QKD PERFORMANCE

A. Modal excitation due to multi-mode fiber coupling

The stability of polarization on short timescales is crucial when considering QKD applications that build on polarization encoding. Coupling from a SMF into a MMF via a free-space channel leads to the excitation of a high number of spatial modes. As a result, the signal transmission in MMF suffers from non-uniform polarization evolution of the guided modes and depolarization [17]. To investigate these effects and possible mitigation techniques, we measured the polarization extinction ratio (PER) of a horizontally polarized signal at 1410 nm after coupling from a SMF to a MMF via a 10-cm long free-space link. The MMF had a core diameter of 25- μm and a length of 3 m. A free-space polarimeter with a single measurement basis (**H/V**) was employed to retrieve the PER. As Fig. 4(a) shows, the PER is only 3.9 dB (ϵ) if no additional impairment mitigation measures are considered. We then constructed a mode filter by coiling the MMF around a 2.5 cm thick rod, using the number of windings as a design parameter that trades against an increase in insertion loss. This mode filter was inserted directly before the

Fig. 5. (a) QBER and per-detector raw-key rate for a purely fiber-based link, a SMF-to-MMF FSO link without mode filter and a SMF-to-MMF link with mode filter for (a) an I/Q polarization-encoded QKD signal at 1410 nm, (b) at 1550.5 nm and (c) for encoding using a PIC at 1550.5 nm.

polarimeter in an attempt to mitigate depolarization by increasing the absorption of higher-order modes in the fiber through coiling [18]. The effect of mode filtering is reported in Fig. 4(a). We see a steady increase in PER, which reaches a large value of 19.7 dB for seven windings (β). An insertion loss of 4.6 dB is incurred for this layout of the mode filter. We consider this design as the optimum, considering the drastic increase for a higher number of windings. The described stripping of higher-order modes mainly depends on the coiling and fiber diameter, as well as on the wavelength. It could in principle be applied to MMFs with larger core diameters. However, we were unable to achieve satisfying results regarding loss and achievable QBER for our 50- μm MMF, which can be attributed to the much higher number of supported propagation modes compared to the 25- μm MMF.

Additionally, we monitored the polarization state for this free-space SMF-to-MMF coupling and compared the stability of the state when either omitting or adopting mode filtering. Further comparison is made with SMF-to-SMF coupling. Exemplary polarization drifts over the course of 1 minute are presented in Fig. 4(b). While the SMF-to-SMF configuration shows a low polarization drift of 6 mrad/s together with a very small spread of the state on the Poincaré sphere due to its high PER of 30.4 dB, relating to a negligible depolarization, the SMF-to-MMF link without filter shows a much faster drift of 240 mrad/s in a donut-like shape, as shown in Fig. 4(b). By introducing the mode filter the spot size can be significantly compressed and the drift reduces to 74 mrad/s. Simple mode filtering can therefore constitute a suitable mitigation method when a MMF is employed at the receiver terminal.

B. QKD performance over indoor FSO link

In a next step, we compared the performance for polarization encoding based on the I/Q modulator and the PIC implementation. This evaluation is conducted at the two wavelengths channels λ_{Q2} and λ_{Q4} in three different scenarios: (i) over a 20-m long SMF link (\blacktriangle in Fig. 5), (ii) over a 6-m long indoor FSO link coupling from SMF to a 1-m long 25- μm MMF patchcord without mode filtering (\bullet) and (iii) when coupling to a 3-m long 25- μm MMF patchcord with present mode filtering (\blacklozenge). These measurements were performed in our lab at a background irradiance of ~ 800 lux. For all three scenarios the

Fig. 6. (a) QKD performance as a function of the optical excess link loss for the 63-m outdoor FSO link and (b) comparison for the three chosen E-band CWDM channel wavelengths designated for QKD operation. (c) Investigation of FSO QKD stability.

QBER and raw-key rate were evaluated as a function of the optical budget between the air interfaces of the transmitter and receiver.

In scenario (i) all three wavelength and modulator combinations perform similarly well over the fiber-based reference link. The compatible optical budgets (OB) are 23.6 dB (λ_{Q2} , *I/Q*, Fig. 5(a)), 22.7 dB (λ_{Q4} , *I/Q*, Fig. 5(b)) and 24.8 dB (λ_{Q4} , PIC, Fig. 5(c)) before surpassing the QBER limit of 11%, which is considered the cut-off for secure-key extraction of the chosen polarization-based BB84 protocol [19]. However, in the case of $\lambda_{Q4} = 1550.5$ nm, the minimum QBER at an optical budget of 0 dB is $\sim 2.4\%$, while it is $\sim 3.3\%$ when transmitting at $\lambda_{Q2} = 1410$ nm. We believe this to be a result of the employed *I/Q* modulator, which is intended for C-band operation and therefore not optimized for the remote E-band wavelength that is detuned by 120 nm from the spectral design window of the LiNbO₃-based *I/Q* modulator. At the same time, we measure similar per-detector raw-key rates for all three scenarios at an optical budget of 0 dB.

Scenario (ii), which includes the FSO link yet without mode filter, leads to comparable raw-key rates when the loss over the FSO link is accounted for. However, for all three transmitter setups the OB at the QBER cut-off is significantly reduced to 15.5, 17.5 and 17 dB, respectively. In all three configurations this can be attributed to the earlier discussed polarization evolution in MMFs, which increases the QBER significantly (\bullet vs. \blacktriangle).

If the mode-filter is added on the receiver side, as introduced through scenario (iii), a significant reduction can be accomplished for the QBER penalty (\blacklozenge). For an OB of 0 dB the reduction corresponds to 2% (λ_{Q2} , *I/Q*), 1% (λ_{Q4} , *I/Q*) and 2.5% (λ_{Q4} , PIC). However, this improvement comes at the expense of additional filtering loss, leading to reduced raw-key rates. Since the mode filter was optimized for 1410 nm, this is the only setting where the OB at the QBER cut-off again increases to 17.8 dB – despite the reduced key-rate. For the two C-band configurations operating at λ_{Q4} , an increased mode filter loss prevents an increase of the OB due to lower raw-key rates. However, we would like to stress that the length of the MMF in scenarios (ii) and (iii) differ by a factor of 3. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the PER for a 3-m long MMF patchcord without filtering is only 3.9 dB, which prevents us from achieving a QBER below the cut-off. Therefore, we opted for a 1-m long MMF when addressing scenario (ii) in order to strike a comparison with the mode-filtered reception of scenario (iii). The presented results indicate that mode filtering is indeed an effective mitigation technique as it enables a significant increase in MMF reach that bridges the gap between the environmentally exposed receiver-side air interface and a possibly more centralized quantum state analyzer.

In addition, the PIC-based state encoder proves to perform superior to the *I/Q* modulator alternative, yielding an OB that is increased by 2.1 and 2.8 dB for the fiber-based reference link and the mode-filtered FSO link, respectively. At the same time the minimum QBER is lowered by 1.6%. This superiority of the PIC when compared to the *I/Q* modulator is mainly attributed to the improved polarization encoder layout of the former and improved thermal stability.

SOLAR-BLIND OPERATION OF AN OUTDOOR FSO QKD LINK

The performance evaluation for the outdoor FSO QKD link was conducted on a single day in autumn with weak turbulence. Figure 2(c) reports the evaluation periods of the three CWDM channels λ_{Q1-3} in the E-band during that day, whose solar irradiance is patterned by light clouds in the morning and late afternoon, and full sunshine with an irradiance of up to 42.9 klux during noon, at which the temperature reached ~ 18 °C. During this day, we evaluated the three receiving fiber configurations mentioned in Table 1 (λ_{Q1} to λ_{Q3}) over our 63-m long rooftop setup.

The adoption of a SMF at the receiving air interface quickly revealed that environmental effects prevent stable SMF-to-SMF coupling over the FSO link. We were not able to obtain a link loss of <24 dB without active beam alignment due to >10 dB fading in the received optical power at an average link loss of 30 dB, even for short timescales of a few minutes. We attribute

Fig. 7. (a) E-band QKD performance under co-existence with a classical C-band data channel. (b) BER performance for classical data transmission over the FSO link.

this to the change in solar influx, leading to thermal expansion and compression of our opto-mechanic support installations for the transmitting and receiving FSO terminals. This rendered the SMF as unsuitable for a low-complexity FSO QKD setup. On the other hand, we achieved a link loss of 7 dB for the 1-m long 50- μm OM4 MMF as the receiving fiber. However, we were unable to reach a QBER below 19% for this configuration, rendering it unsuitable despite its large core diameter and therefore good coupling efficiency and enhanced turbulence resiliency. However, if an ideal mode filter for the 50- μm MMF would be available, we would expect an increase of up to 10.8 dB in optical budget, depending on the SPAD saturation limit. For the 25- μm MMF that is less prone to multi-mode propagation impairments, we obtained a FSO link loss of 17.8 dB. Yet, we were able to achieve QBER values below the threshold of 11% for a short MMF length of 1 m. By optimizing the mode filtering before the state analyzer at the receiver, we reached QBER values that fall within a 1% penalty of a fully fiber-based reference link that bridges the 63-m FSO distance with SMF fiber. At the same time, there was no re-alignment of the FSO link necessary during the whole measurement campaign, rendering the 25- μm MMF as suitable for alignment-tolerant large-core FSO links.

In a next step we evaluated the average QBER and raw-key rate for the three quantum channel wavelengths as a function of the tolerable optical excess loss (EL) for the FSO channel. The corresponding results are reported in Fig. 6(a). Here, an EL of 0 dB relates to the situation where photons are transmitted at $\mu_Q = 0.1$ photons/symbol at the transmitting air interface and an optical channel loss of 17.8 dB. For λ_{Q1} and λ_{Q2} we reach comparable per-detector raw-key rates of 3.9 kb/s and 3.7 kb/s at a QBER of 7.6% and 7.9%, respectively (\bullet , \blacklozenge). The QBER slightly increases to 9.4% for λ_{Q3} , for which we also see an increased raw-key rate of 4.3 kb/s (\blacktriangle). This rise is mainly attributed to the increased in-band noise due to the stronger solar background signature at 1430 nm, as it can be inferred from Fig. 2(b). From these results we estimate secure-key rates of 869, 745 and 435 b/s per detector for the E-band wavelength channels λ_{Q1} to λ_{Q3} . According to the NIST-limit for AES-GCM key renewal [20], which foresees the use of one 256-bit key per 64 GB volume of data, these secure-key rates allow to secure 1.65, 1.49 and 0.87 Tb/s of classical channel capacity, respectively. This suggests the QKD channels at 1390 nm and 1410 nm as the preferred choice for solar-blind operation. For both channels we can accommodate an additional EL of ~ 7.6 dB before surpassing the 11% QBER threshold. This provides a comfortable link margin for the passive layout of the FSO channel. The increased total OB of 25.4 dB compared to the indoor reference link budget of 17.8 dB can be mainly attributed to the $>25\%$ reduced dark count rate of the employed SPAD for the outdoor measurement, whose influence is significant at low count rates of 1 kb/s/detector.

Figure 6(b) summarizes the channel-specific performance for an EL of 0 dB. The minimum achievable QBER (\bullet) shows a clear correlation to the relative solar influx (+) at the large-core fiber, indicating the penalty incurred for the CWDM channel at λ_{Q3} .

Figure 6(c) investigates the stability of the link performance for continuous operation and real-time evaluation at EL settings of 1.6 and 4.6 dB. There are no signs of sporadic effects noticeable for the QKD performance, such as caused by the excitation of higher-order modes due to vibrations or wind. The visibly increasing QBER is attributed to polarization drift along the 200-m feeder fiber between the lab and, especially, the roof-top installation that includes an environmentally exposed cable duct in which part of the feeder fiber is deployed. Furthermore, we do not see any increase in the observed QBER fluctuations due to atmospheric effects, such as turbulence, for the outdoor setup. For example, we yield an average QBER of $8.65 \pm 0.32\%$ at a raw-key rate of 3.04 ± 0.04 kb/s during the first minute of our measurement, which is comparable to the SMF reference measurement for 1410 nm for which we achieve a QBER of $8.89 \pm 0.32\%$ at a raw-key rate of 3.32 ± 0.04 kb/s (\blacktriangle in Fig. 5(a)).

Finally, we also investigated the co-existence of a simultaneously transmitted C-band channel with the quantum signal, for which Fig. 7(a) reports the QKD performance. Without any classical channel, the QBER is drifting only slightly due to the aforementioned polarization transform induced by the feeder fiber. We then activated the classical data stream in a burst-like transmission, for which the 45-s long active data bursts (κ) led to an average increase in QBER of $\sim 0.7\%$ during co-existence. For the classical data channel, whose BER performance is reported in Fig. 7(b) as a function of the ROP, we obtained a reception

sensitivity of -37.4 dBm at the Reed-Solomon(255,239) forward error correction (FEC) threshold of 2×10^{-4} . Figure 7(b) evidences the good data transmission performance through a clearly open eye diagram. Moreover, there is no BER floor for three orders of magnitude below the FEC threshold. The accomplished sensitivity corresponds to a power margin of more than 15 dB for the FSO link, as defined as the range in optical power between delivered signal and reception sensitivity. Therefore, we do not expect the FEC level to be surpassed by variations in ROP.

CONCLUSION

We have experimentally demonstrated a low-complexity FSO link for polarization-encoded QKD, achieving a simplified and alignment-tolerant operation through the use of large-core fibers at the receiving air interface. We determined the MMF with 25- μ m core diameter as the most suitable candidate for the terrestrial FSO link since depolarization due to the excitation of higher-order modes can be effectively suppressed by applying simple mode-filtering techniques, while also enhancing the alignment and turbulence tolerance. The reduced spatial filtering of sunlight photons due to the use of large-core fibers at the receiving link end has been mitigated by a spectral allocation of the quantum channels in the water-absorption region of the atmosphere at the E-band. Through this approach we achieved a secure-key rate of 869 b/s/detector for a 63-m long terrestrial free-space link, operating in solar-blind manner during full sunshine. In particular, we find the two CWDM channels at 1390 nm and 1410 nm as two suitable wavelengths for QKD operation. We further demonstrated secure-key generation in co-existence with a 1 Gb/s classical C-band data channel. In addition, we investigated a PIC design dedicated to polarization modulation at 1550 nm, featuring a similar performance as obtained for the employed I/Q -modulator. Apart from the more compact footprint, all modulation electrodes of the PIC are RF-matched, which allows for signal bandwidths >1 GHz. Therefore, we expect a PIC designed for 1400 nm operation to outperform the currently employed I/Q -modulator in rate as well as in QBER. We believe that the chosen approach enables a considerable simplification of short-range terrestrial FSO QKD installations operating at full daylight, especially in combination with a reduction in size by means of photonic integration.

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